

EXAMINING THE INFLUENCE OF PRINCIPALS' COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES ON TEACHERS' EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between principals' communication practices and teacher emotional distress in thirteen (13) public schools within Brgy. Mamatid, Division of Cabuyao Laguna. A quantitative approach with a descriptive research design was employed. Data was collected through a survey using an adapted questionnaire distributed to teachers. The questionnaire assessed perceptions of principals' communication styles (aggressive, assertive, open, inclusive) and teacher emotional distress. The hypothesis, tested at a significance level of 0.05, examined the impact of communication practices on emotional distress. Statistical analysis using regression analysis explored the influence of communication styles on teachers' emotional well-being. The findings revealed that all four communication styles examined (aggressive, assertive, open, and inclusive) had some influence on teachers' emotional distress. However, the effect size for each style was relatively small, suggesting a weak individual association. Interestingly, the positive B coefficients for assertive, open, and inclusive communication styles indicated a potential counterintuitive trend - that these seemingly positive communication styles might be linked to slightly higher emotional distress. However, it's important to consider that these effects were very weak. The analysis involved examining the relationship between principals' communication practices and teachers' emotional distress through regression analysis of variance. The resulting F-value of 0.179, with a corresponding p-value of 0.946, was obtained. Given that this p-value exceeds the standard alpha threshold of 0.05, we accept the null hypothesis. This outcome indicates that the collective impact of communication practices variables does not significantly influence teachers' emotional distress levels.

Keywords: *Communication Practices, Principals, Teacher Emotional Distress, Teacher well-Being*

INTRODUCTION

The most common methods employed by schools to fulfill their mission of providing pupils with a top-notch education are communication tactics. Thus, their trusted practitioners are educators and school administrators. Problems may arise in certain schools when the principal disregards explicit communication protocols, resulting in inadequate teacher comprehension (Krauss, 2018). Social support has been identified as one of the most crucial workplace support systems, and it can help instructors mitigate and counteract the negative effects (Almeida et al., 2021).

To give them the support they require, the people in their near vicinity—especially their immediate employer, the principal—must meaningfully, regularly, and appropriately communicate with them. Furthermore, Tatar (2021) indicates that instructors most commonly seek assistance from friends, colleagues, and the school principal. In addition to being the leaders of the group, principals motivate and assist teachers in providing excellent instruction and doing various other duties in the workplace..

The researcher decided to carry out the study to identify relevant literature on educational management and associate it with related psychological and organizational literature in order to have a deeper understanding and realization of the roles of the principal in providing emotional support for the teachers when not distressed emotional distress arises.

Research Questions

The general problem of the study is, “How may the impact of communication practices of principals on emotional distress of the teachers be analyzed?” Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. How may the communication practices of principals be described in terms of;
 - 1.1. aggressive communication;
 - 1.2. assertive communication;
 - 1.3. open communication; and
 - 1.4. inclusive communication?
2. What is the level of emotional distress of the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. physical indicators;
 - 2.2. sleep indicators;
 - 2.3. behavioral indicators;
 - 2.4. emotional indicators; and,
 - 2.5. personal habits indicators?
3. Do the principals’ communication practices exert significant impact on teachers’ emotional distress?

4. What intervention program may be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used of the descriptive-correlational method of research to determine the communication practices of the principals and what significant impact does it imply on the emotional distress of the teachers. The professional judgments were supported by facts or a scientific basis, and an order was used to get comprehensive evidence. The relationship between variables is systematically studied through correlational research.

Research Locale

The study focused on the impact of communication practices of principals on the emotional distress of the teachers in Bulacan. The study included Thirteen (13) principals and Two Hundred Four (204) teachers in private schools located in Brgy. Mamatid, Cabuyao Laguna. This was composed of Twelve (13) Private Schools during the school year 2022-2023.

The study determined the communication practices in terms of aggressive, assertive, open and inclusive communication practice by the school principals. The teachers evaluated their principals' communication practices using a standardized questionnaire; meanwhile the teachers' level of emotional distress was identified using a self-survey standardized instrument performed by the teachers.

Population and Sample

The respondents of the study were the principals and teachers of public schools located in the Divison of Cabuyao Laguna, who are presently employed in the academic year 2022-2023.

Table 1

Respondents of the study

Public Schools	No. of Teachers	No. of Principals	Total Respondents
A	35	1	36
B	10	1	11
C	14	1	15
D	21	1	22
E	7	1	8
F	7	1	8
G	15	1	16
H	13	1	14
I	29	1	30
J	7	1	8

K	13	1	14
L	20	1	21
M	13	1	14
Total	204	13	217

Table 1 showed the distribution of respondents in each corresponding school. The respondents of the study were from the thirteen (13) private schools established at Brgy, Mamatid Division of Cabuyao, Laguna.

Research Instrument

The instrument was adopted from a standardized tool of a research that measures the Principals' Communication Practices (Berkovich & Eyal 2018).

The 28-item questionnaire is divided into (4) four parts that corresponds to the communication practices of the principals as to: aggressive communication, assertive communication, open communication and inclusive communication. The instrument recorded a 0.75 reliability coefficient (Akinwale & Okotoni, 2018).

Validation of Questionnaire

This questionnaire measures four aspects of a principal's communication style: aggressive, assertive, open, and inclusive communication. The validation evidence provided is a reliability coefficient of 0.75 (Akinwale & Okotoni, 2018).

In determining the teachers' level of emotional distress, Stress indicators instrument with a Cronbach's alpha 0.86 was utilized (Chan et al., 2021).

Data Gathering Procedure

The method of data gathering was questionnaire method. Each of the respondents was given a structured set of questions. In gathering the data, the researcher carried out the following procedure:

1. An approval sheet was secured from the school and from the Department of Education Schools Superintendent to conduct the study.
2. A letter was sent to the School Heads to ask permission in the conduct of proposed study.
3. Upon the approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the respondents.
4. The researcher checked if all the questionnaires are answered completely.
5. Lastly, the data were subjected to computations, analysis, and interpretations.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The data collected was tabulated and processed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The following statistical measures such as mean procedures and multiple correlation and regression procedures were employed.

Specifically,

1. The data on the Level of Principals' Communication Practices was measured using mean procedures with the following scale:

Scale	Range	Description Rating
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Practiced
4	3.50-4.49	Practiced
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced
2	1.50-2.49	Not Practiced
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Not Practiced

2. The data on the Teachers' Level of Emotional Distress were assessed using mean procedure with the following scale:

Scale	Range	Stress Levels
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Distressed
4	3.50-4.49	Distressed
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Distressed
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Distressed
1	1.00-1.49	Not Distressed

3. Regression Analysis was used to determine the impact of the Principal's Communication Practices on the Emotional Distress of the teachers.

RESULTS

Communication Practices of Principals

Communication plays a central role in schools, acting as the foundation for all interactions (Wood, 2021). Encompassing various functions such as informing, instructing, and building relationships, communication extends beyond classrooms (Wood, 2022).

It occurs within discussions between teachers and students, during extracurricular activities, and throughout the school environment, involving students, teachers, staff, and the principal. Effective communication among these groups is essential for a smooth-running school that prioritizes student learning and professional development for its teachers and staff (Champoux, 2021). This collaborative atmosphere fosters a child-centered environment, promoting effective learning and professional growth (Tutar & Yilmaz, 2021).

Aggressive Communication

Aggressive communication, characterized by personal attacks and blame, can significantly hinder interpersonal relationships and communication effectiveness (Rosenfeld et al., 2019). It fosters a hostile environment, impedes productive dialogue, and erodes trust, respect, and collaboration (Rosenfeld et al., 2019). To cultivate healthy communication dynamics, individuals should prioritize assertiveness, emotional regulation, and empathy.

Recognizing the detrimental impact of aggressive communication and choosing more mindful and empathetic forms of expression allows individuals to foster more harmonious and effective interactions (Rosenfeld et al., 2019).

Table 2

Communication Practices in terms of aggressive communication

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Use of threats to motivate teachers to work	1.67	Not Practiced
2. Use of obscene language when relating with teachers	1.67	Not Practiced
3. Easily find faults in whatever teachers do	1.71	Not Practiced
4. Display of anger when displeases by teachers' actions	1.71	Not Practiced
5. Transfer of aggression when things are not happening as expected	1.57	Not Practiced
6. Dislike being confronted by teachers' in a general meeting	1.76	Not Practiced
7. Use query and derogatory words when teachers make mistakes on the job	1.67	Not Practiced
Average	1.68	Not Practiced

Table 2 shows that the communication practices of principals in terms of aggressive communication got a not practiced rating as evidenced by 1.68 mean percentage score.

This was specially manifested through the following: principals do not use threats to motivate teachers to work (1.67), they do not use obscene language when relating with teachers (1.67), they do not easily find faults in whatever teachers do (1.71), do not display of anger when displeases by teachers' actions (1.71), do not transfer of aggression when things are not happening as expected (1.57), they dislike being confronted by teachers' in a general meeting (1.76), and they do not use query and derogatory words when teachers make mistakes on the job (1.67).

Assertive Communication

Assertive communication is a vital skill necessary for effective and respectful interactions in both personal and professional settings (Rathbone, 2020). By clearly

conveying our thoughts, feelings, and needs in a confident and direct manner, we can assert our boundaries, express our opinions, and advocate for ourselves without resorting to aggressive or passive behaviors. Assertive communication fosters mutual understanding and promotes healthy relationships by promoting honesty, transparency, and respect for oneself and others (Rathbone, 2020).

It requires self-awareness, self-confidence, and emotional intelligence to effectively communicate assertively while also recognizing and validating the perspectives and feelings of others (Rathbone, 2020). By honing this skill, individuals can navigate conversations and conflicts with grace, assertiveness, and integrity, ultimately leading to positive outcomes and harmonious relationships.

Table 3

Communication Practices in terms of assertive communication

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Fluency in the clarification of ideas	4.24	Practiced
2. Clearly express a chain of thought during argument of a point	4.10	Practiced
3. Taking the lead in a conversation in the school	4.24	Practiced
4. Standing for the rights in school when necessary	4.43	Practiced
5. Determines the direction of conversation in a meeting	4.43	Practiced
6. Giving concise and unambiguous messages to teachers	3.86	Practiced
7. Respecting the rights and dignity of teachers in the school	4.48	Practiced
Average	4.25	Practiced

Table 3 revealed that the communication practices in terms of assertive communication got a practiced rating as evidenced by 4.25 mean percentage score. This was evidenced through the following characteristics of principals: they have fluency in the clarification of ideas (4.24), clearly express a chain of thought during argument of a point (4.10), taking the lead in a conversation in the school (4.24), standing for the rights in school when necessary (4.43), determines the direction of conversation in a meeting (4.43), giving concise and unambiguous messages to teachers (3.86), respecting the rights and dignity of teachers in the school (4.48).

Open Communication

Open communication is crucial in personal relationships, professional settings, and personal life. Transparency and honesty build trust, resolve conflicts, and foster understanding. It fosters a collaborative environment for ideas exchange and problem-solving. Constructive feedback promotes personal growth (Aviram & Schroeder, 2023).

Table 4

Communication Practices in terms of open communication

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Talk freely with all the teachers	4.38	Practiced
2. Teachers are allowed to freely express themselves in meetings	4.43	Practiced
3. Teachers feel free to discuss challenges facing them in teaching	4.33	Practiced
4. Encourage teachers even when students are not performing as expected	4.43	Practiced
5. Encourage teachers to give feedback on policies and programs of school	4.43	Practiced
6. Showing of Concern to teachers' challenges in a professional way	4.52	Strongly Practiced
7. Often show a lot of understanding for other people's problem	4.38	Practiced
Average	4.42	Practiced

Analysis of data in Table 4 showed that the communication practices in terms of open communication got a practiced rating as evidenced by 4.42 mean percentage score. Specifically, they talk freely with all the teachers (4.38), teachers are allowed to freely express themselves in meetings (4.43), teachers feel free to discuss challenges facing them in teaching (4.33), encourage teachers even when students are not performing as expected (4.43), encourage teachers to give feedback on policies and programs of school (4.43), showing of Concern to teachers' challenges in a professional way (4.52), and often show a lot of understanding for other people's problem (4.38).

Inclusive Communication

Inclusive communication involves fostering an environment where all individuals feel valued, respected, and understood regardless of their background, abilities, or beliefs (Caldwell, 2020). It requires using language and methods that are accessible to everyone and actively seeking to include diverse perspectives and voices in conversations and decision-making processes.

Table 5

Communication Practices in terms of inclusive communication

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Making opinions counts in day-to-day decision that affect teachers' work	4.14	Practiced
2. Inclusion of one or more teachers in the school management	4.29	Practiced
3. Principal seeks for teacher's and inputs in school programs	4.19	Practiced
4. Showing of admiration for teachers' work	4.43	Practiced

5. Teachers are allowed to participate in the planning of school work/policy	4.48	Practiced
6. Staff are made to be aware and have understanding of all school procedures and policies	4.38	Practiced
7. Making the school environment comfortable for all the teachers	4.52	Strongly Practiced
Average	4.35	Practiced

Table 5 shows that the communication practices in terms of inclusive communication got a practiced rating as evidenced by 4.35 mean percentage score. This indicates that principals are making opinions counts in day-to-day decision that affect teachers' work (4.14), inclusion of one or more teachers in the school management (4.29), principal seeks for teacher's and inputs in school programs (4.19), showing of admiration for teachers' work (4.43), teachers are allowed to participate in the planning of school work/policies (4.48), staff are made to be aware and have understanding of all school procedures and policies (4.38), and making the school environment comfortable for all the teachers (4.52).

Emotional Distress of the Teachers

According to Ozoemena et al., (2021) stress can arise from various sources, these sources can be broadly categorized as personal experiences, environmental factors, and changes in roles. They all have the potential to trigger emotional responses and lead to emotional distress. This study specifically focuses on the emotional distress experienced by teachers.

Changes in a teacher's role can also be stressful. This might include promotions, increased workloads, or expanded responsibilities (Man et al.,2020). Negative past experiences, such as those with challenging students or classroom management issues, can also contribute to teacher stress (Braun 2022). The impact of these stressors extends beyond a teacher's mental state, affecting their overall emotional well-being (Man et al., 2020).

Table 6
Emotional distress in terms of physical indicators

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. My body feels tense all over.	2.60	Moderately Distressed
2. I have a nervous sweat or sweaty palms.	2.12	Slightly Distressed
3. I have a hard time feeling really relaxed.	2.79	Moderately Distressed
4. I have severe or chronic lower back pain.	2.72	Moderately Distressed
5. I get severe or chronic headaches.	2.56	Moderately Distressed
6. I get tension or muscle spasms in my face, jaw, neck or shoulders	2.35	Slightly Distressed
7. My stomach quivers or feels upset	2.31	Slightly Distressed
8. I get skin rashes or itching.	2.03	Slightly Distressed

9. I have problems with my bowels (constipation, diarrhea).	2.17	Slightly Distressed
10. I need to urinate more than most people.	2.23	Slightly Distressed
11. My ulcer bothers me.	1.57	Slightly Distressed
12. I feel short of breath after mild exercise like climbing up four flights of stairs.	2.59	Moderately Distressed
13. Compared to most people, I have a very small or a very large appetite.	2.42	Slightly Distressed
14. My weight is more than 15 pounds recommended for a person my height and build.	2.50	Moderately Distressed
15. I smoke tobacco.	1.17	Not Distressed
16. I get sharp chest pains when I'm physically active.	1.80	Slightly Distressed
17. I lack physical energy.	2.36	Slightly Distressed
18. When I'm resting, my heart beats more than 100 times a minute.	1.96	Slightly Distressed
19. Because of my busy schedule I miss at least two meals during the week.	2.03	Slightly Distressed
20. I don't really plan my meals for balanced nutrition.	2.46	Slightly Distressed
21. I spend less than 3 hours a week getting vigorous physical exercise (running, playing basketball, tennis, swimming, etc).	2.20	Slightly Distressed
Average	2.24	Slightly Distressed

Table 6 shows that the emotional distress of teachers in terms of physical indicators got slightly distressed rating as shown by the mean percentage score of 2.24. This was manifested through the following experiences of the teachers: Teachers' body feels tense all over (2.60), they have a nervous sweat or sweaty palms (2.12), have a hard time feeling really relaxed (2.79), have severe or chronic lower back pain (2.72), get severe or chronic headaches (2.56), get tension or muscle spasms in my face, jaw, neck or shoulders (2.35), their stomach quivers or feels upset (2.31), they get skin rashes or itching (2.03), they have problems with their bowels (constipation, diarrhea) (2.17), they need to urinate more than most people (2.23), some of them got ulcers and it bothers them (1.57), they feel short of breath after mild exercise like climbing up four flights of stairs (2.59), compared to most people, they have a very small or a very large appetite (2.42), their weight is more than 15 pounds recommended for a person their height and build (2.50), they do not smoke tobacco (1.17), they get sharp chest pains when I'm physically active (1.80), they lack physical energy (2.36), when they are resting, their hearts beat more than 100 times a minute (1.96), because of their busy schedule, they missed at least two meals during the week (2.03), they don't really plan my meals for balanced nutrition (2.46), they spend less than 3 hours a week getting vigorous physical exercise (running, playing basketball, tennis, swimming, etc) (2.20).

Table 7

Emotional distress in terms of sleep indicators

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I have trouble falling asleep.	2.59	Moderately Distressed
2. I take pills to get to sleep.	1.27	Not Distressed
3. I have nightmares or repeated bad dreams.	1.64	Slightly Distressed
4. I wake up at least once in the middle of the night for no apparent reason.	2.42	Slightly Distressed
5. No matter how much sleep I get, I awake feeling tired	2.36	Slightly Distressed
Average	2.06	Slightly Distressed

Table 7 revealed that emotional distress in terms of sleep indicators got a 2.06 mean percentage score. Specifically, they have trouble falling asleep (2.59), they take pills to get to sleep (1.27), have nightmares or repeated bad dreams (1.64), they wake up at least once in the middle of the night for no apparent reason (2.42), and no matter how much sleep they get, they awake feeling tired (2.36).

Table 8

Emotional distress in terms of behavioral indicators

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I stutter or get tongue tied when I talk to other people.	2.02	Slightly Distressed
2. I try to work while I'm eating lunch.	2.43	Slightly Distressed
3. I have to work late.	2.58	Moderately Distressed
4. I go to work even when I feel sick.	2.94	Moderately Distressed
5. I have to bring work home.	3.58	Most of the time
6. I drink alcohol or use drugs to relax.	1.19	Not Distressed
7. I have more than two beers, eight ounces of wine or three ounces of hard liquor a day.	1.15	Not Distressed
8. When I drink, I like to get really drunk	1.15	Not Distressed
9. I get drunk or "high" with other drugs more than once a week.	1.12	Not Distressed
10. When I'm feeling high from alcohol or drugs I will drive a motor vehicle.	1.12	Not Distressed
11. I tend to stumble when walking, or have more accidents than other people.	1.24	Not Distressed
12. In any given week, I take at least one prescription drug without the recommendation of a physician, e.g. amphetamines, barbiturates.	1.22	Not Distressed
13. I have problems with my sex life.	1.37	Not Distressed
14. At least once during the week I will make bets for money.	1.26	Not Distressed

15. After dinner I spend more time alone do talking with my family or friends.	2.56	Moderately Distressed
16. I arrive at work late.	1.86	Slightly Distressed
17. At least once during the week I have a shouting match with a co-worker or supervisor.	1.27	Not Distressed
Average	1.77	Slightly Distressed

Table 8 shows that emotional distress of teachers in terms behavior indicators got a slightly distressed rating 1.77 mean percentage score. Particularly, they slightly stutter or get tongue tied when they talk to other people (2.02), try to work while they are eating lunch (2.43), have to work late (2.58), go to work even when they feel sick (2.94), they have to bring work home (3.58), they drink alcohol or use drugs to relax (1.19), they have more than two beers, eight ounces of wine or three ounces of hard liquor a day (1.15), when they drink, they like to get really drunk (1.15), they get drunk or "high" with other drugs more than once a week (1.12), when they are feeling high from alcohol or drugs they will drive a motor vehicle (1.12), they tend to stumble when walking, or have more accidents than other people (1.24), in any given week, they take at least one prescription drug without the recommendation of a physician, e.g. amphetamines, barbiturates (1.22), they have problems with their sex life (1.37), at least once during the week they will make bets for money (1.26), after dinner they spend more time alone do talking with their family or friends (2.56), they arrive at work late (1.86), at least once during the week they have a shouting match with a co-worker or supervisor (1.27).

Table 9
Emotional distress in terms of emotional indicators

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I have found the best way to deal with hassles and problems is to consciously avoid thinking or talking about them	2.72	Moderately Distressed
2. I have trouble remembering things	2.51	Moderately Distressed
3. I feel anxious or frightened about problems I can't really describe	2.30	Slightly Distressed
4. I worry a lot	2.36	Slightly Distressed
5. It is important for me not to show my emotions to my family	2.63	Moderately Distressed
6. It is hard for me to relax at home	2.02	Slightly Distressed
7. It's best if I don't tell even my closest friend how I'm really feeling	2.21	Slightly Distressed
8. I find it hard to talk when I get excited	2.13	Slightly Distressed
9. I feel very angry inside	1.92	Slightly Distressed
10. I have temper outbursts I can't control	1.92	Slightly Distressed
11. When people criticize me, even in friendly, constructive way, I feel offended.	1.99	Slightly Distressed
12. I feel extremely sensitive and irritable	2.08	Slightly Distressed

13. My emotions change unpredictably and without any apparent reason	1.98	Slightly Distressed
14. I feel like I really can't trust anyone	2.08	Slightly Distressed
15. I feel like other people don't understand me.	2.20	Slightly Distressed
16. I really don't feel good about myself	1.92	Slightly Distressed
17. Generally, I am not optimistic about my future.	1.87	Slightly Distressed
18. I feel very tired and disinterested in life	1.81	Slightly Distressed
19. Impulsive behavior has caused me problems	1.93	Slightly Distressed
20. I have felt so bad that I thought of hurting myself	1.60	Slightly Distressed
21. When I have an important personal problem that I can't solve myself, I do not seek professional help	1.96	Slightly Distressed
Average	2.10	Slightly Distressed

Findings in Table 9 indicated that emotional distress in terms of emotional indicators got a slightly distressed rating as evidenced by 2.10. They have found the best way to deal with hassles and problems is to consciously avoid thinking or talking about them (2.72), they have trouble remembering things (2.51), feel anxious or frightened about problems they can't really describe (2.30), they worry a lot (2.36), it is important for me not to show my emotions to my family (2.63), it is hard for me to relax at home (2.02), it is best if they don't tell even their closest friend how their really feeling (2.21), they find it hard to talk when they get excited (2.13), they feel very angry inside (1.92), they have temper outbursts they can't control (1.92), when people criticize them, even in friendly, constructive way, they feel offended (1.99), they feel extremely sensitive and irritable (2.08), their emotions change unpredictably and without any apparent reason (1.98), they feel like they really can't trust anyone (2.08), feel like other people don't understand them. (2.20), really don't feel good about themselves (1.92), generally, they not optimistic about their future (1.87), they feel very tired and disinterested in life (1.81), impulsive behavior has caused them problems (1.93), they have felt so bad that they thought of hurting themselves (1.60), when they have an important personal problem that they can't solve themselves, they do not seek professional help (1.96).

Table 10
Emotional distress in terms of personal habits indicators

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I spend less than three hours a week working on a hobby of mine.	2.60	Moderately Distressed
2. I spend less than one hour a week writing personal letters, writing in a diary or writing creatively.	1.94	Slightly Distressed
3. I spend less than 30 minutes a week talking casually with my neighbors.	2.39	Slightly Distressed
4. I lack time to read the daily newspaper.	2.61	Moderately Distressed

5. I watch television for entertainment more than one hour a day.	2.90	Moderately Distressed
6. I drive in a motor vehicle faster than the speed limit for the excitement and challenge of it.	1.57	Slightly Distressed
7. I spend less than 30 minutes a day working toward a life goal or ambition of mine.	2.40	Slightly Distressed
8. My day to day living is not really affected by my religious beliefs or my philosophy of life.	2.39	Slightly Distressed
9. When I feel stressed, it is difficult for me to plan time and activities to constructively release my stress.	2.68	Moderately Distressed
Average	2.39	Slightly Distressed

Findings in Table 10 indicated that emotional distress in terms of personal indicators got a slightly distressed rating as evidenced by 2.39 mean percentage. Specifically, they spend less than three hours a week working on a hobby of mine (2.60), they spend less than one hour a week writing personal letters, writing in a diary or writing creatively (1.94), they spend less than 30 minutes a week talking casually with their neighbors (2.39), they lack time to read the daily newspaper (2.61), watch television for entertainment more than one hour a day (2.90), they drive in a motor vehicle faster than the speed limit for the excitement and challenge of it (1.57), they spend less than 30 minutes a day working toward a life goal or ambition of mine (2.40), their day to day living is not really affected by their religious beliefs or their philosophy of life (2.39), when they feel stressed, it is difficult for them to plan time and activities to constructively release their stress (2.68).

Impact of Communication Practices of Principals on Teachers' Emotional Distress

The study investigated the potential influence of principal communication styles on teacher emotional distress. The researchers hypothesized that communication styles wouldn't significantly impact teachers' well-being. To test this, the researcher employed correlation analysis to assess the strength and direction of any association between communication styles and emotional distress. Regression analysis was then used to estimate how much teacher emotional distress might change with variations in communication styles.

Table 11

Regression analysis of Communication practices of Principals on Teachers Emotional distress

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	2.424	1.466		1.653	0.118

Aggressive communication	0.078	0.286	0.076	0.273	0.788
Assertive communication	0.344	1.177	0.277	0.292	0.774
Open communication	0.635	0.828	0.52	0.766	0.455
Inclusive communication	0.206	1.012	0.178	0.203	0.842
r-square = .196					
r = .0512					
f-value = .179					
p-value = .946					
alpha = .05					

Results of the regression analysis indicate that the four variables of the communication practices of principals affect the teachers' emotional distress in varying extent as shown by the non-zero coefficients. A closer look at the obtained B coefficients, one could deduce that four variables yielded B coefficients of 0.078 (aggressive communication), 0.344 (assertive communication), 0.635 (open communication) and 0.206 (inclusive communication) with associated probability greater than the significance level set at 0.05. This means that aggressive communication, assertive communication, open communication, and inclusive communication affect teachers' emotional distress that for every unit improvement in variables mentioned, teachers' emotional distress can be expected to increase by 0.078, 0.344, 0.635, and 0.206, respectively. All these variables affect the dependent variable but not to a significant extent.

Results of the analysis of variance of the regression of principals' communication practices on teachers' emotional distress revealed an F-value of .179 with a p-value of 0.946. Since the associated probability of the obtained F-value is greater than alpha (0.05), the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the variables of communication practices do not exert significant combined effects on teachers' emotional distress.

Furthermore, the R able to denote multiple correlation coefficient between the different variables as a predictor of the dependent variable. It could be noted that the R is .0512 which indicates a level of prediction while R-square figure is a statistical measure on closeness of the data in regression line as the coefficient of determination or simply the coefficient of multiple determination for multiple regression. It can be indicated that the explanatory powers of the dependent variable of 0.196 implies that 20% of the variation in communication practices of principals is accounted by changes in teachers' emotional distress.

DISCUSSION

This section summarizes and illustrates the results that the researchers have gathered from the study.

1. Communication Practices of Principals

- 1.1. The success of a school hinges on its leader's ability to communicate effectively (Hussein 2020). As the principal, the buck stops with them. To ensure a productive learning environment, clear communication is paramount. This includes establishing the school's mission, goals, and objectives (Hammonds 2022). It also involves implementing the curriculum effectively, facilitating quality instruction, and providing educators with the necessary feedback and support (Hattie, Frey & Clarke 2021).

Additionally, planning plays a crucial role in this process. During this time, the principal outlines the school's overall aim, designs the curriculum, and determines the methods of instruction (Hammonds 2022). Additionally, they establish school policies and rules that are then disseminated to the teachers (Hattie, Frey & Clarke 2021). These procedures create a standardized environment, ensuring everyone understands their roles and expectations. Clear communication minimizes confusion, reduces noncompliance, and fosters a collaborative school community (Hussein 2020).

- 1.2. Effective communication is the cornerstone of any leadership role (Thomas 2019). In an organization, a leader's ability to persistently and consistently communicate their vision is crucial for motivating the team. As the principal, the leader of the school, this is especially important (Sollitto & Cranmer 2019).

Moreover, the principal needs to be the most knowledgeable person regarding the school's vision (Thomas 2019). They must be able to clearly articulate this vision and inspire others to share it. This clarity fosters trust and confidence among staff, as everyone feels aligned towards a common goal. Inconsistent messages, however, can create confusion and division (Sollitto & Cranmer 2019). If instructions change frequently, it can be difficult for staff to adapt, potentially hindering progress.

Therefore, the principal's communication should be clear, consistent, and firm. This demonstrates a deep understanding of the vision and inspires trust in the overall direction of the school.

- 1.3. According to Cui (2021), while educational leadership positions require extensive training and experience principals today face a multitude of stressors that can impede their effectiveness. These stressors often stem from a lack of clear communication, shifting expectations, and insufficient professional development opportunities

Furthermore, principals typically possess advanced degrees and years of experience managing schools (Freilling, et al., 2021). This background equips them with the knowledge and skills to navigate day-to-day operations and even conflicts. As the adage goes, "experience is the best teacher," and principals rely on this experience to handle diverse situations. However, ongoing professional development is crucial to stay up-to-date with educational trends and best practices, particularly in response to the evolving needs of 21st-century learners (Mohamed & Zainal Abidin 2021).

Additionally, when any of these elements - clear communication, stable expectations, or adequate professional development - are lacking, it can create significant challenges for principals (Mohamed & Zainal Abidin 2021). Insufficient knowledge or skills can lead to conflicts and problems that are difficult to resolve quickly. This, in turn, can cause stress not only for the principal but also for the entire school community, especially teachers.

- 1.4. According to Leithwood (2021) a leader must build trust, transparency and credibility among its employees by communicating to them informing what is occurring and preventing destructive rumors. It is the principals' role to prevent a simple complication to develop into a more serious and even destructive dispute. It is important that the principal presents the real score, the present situation and status of the conflict to the group, so trust can be gained from the teachers knowing that their principal is not hiding anything from them. It is also an indication for the teachers that their principal trusts them for the fact that the principal is being transparent to them.

2. Emotional Distress of the Teachers

- 2.1. In the classroom, a teacher's emotions significantly influence their teaching style and effectiveness (Stapleton, Garby & Sabot, 2020). Positive emotions translate to a more active and engaging teacher, while sadness or fatigue might lead to a less enthusiastic and weaker presence (Jennings et al. 2019). Similarly, anger can manifest as impatience and aggression (Lacomba-Trejo et al., 2020).

Stapleton, Garby and Sabot, (2020) delve into the concept of emotional distress in teachers, exploring the individual triggers that lead to stress and the coping mechanisms teachers employ. They emphasize how negative emotional states can lead to teacher dysfunction (Lacomba-Trejo et al., 2020).. When emotionally distressed, teachers might withdraw and contemplate, potentially altering their routines to avoid similar negative experiences (Jennings et al., 2019).

Furthermore, in turn, can hinder their productivity and overall effectiveness (Jennings et al., 2019). These factors include the nature of the students and their classes, time constraints, the educational system itself, school activities, relationships with colleagues, self-esteem, evaluations from superiors, and even the physical work environment (Stapleton, Garby & Sabot, 2020)

To further elaborate, stress from the nature of the students and its classes can be characterized by several conditions; students who are mentally challenged that needs special attention, students who have attitude problem that requires discipline and students who do not tend to comply, and are violators to school policies (Huang et al. 2019).

- 2.2. Daniel et al. (2019) stated that since the main goal of the teachers is to produce competent students, it is their calling and challenge to work hard to achieve this goal building stress over time and for the fact that it requires the teacher to inform and communicate with their students' parents, not all of them will cooperate and for some will put the blame on them instead as the learning-provider.

According to Wassing et al. (2019) some of these parents may not communicate well using foul words and gestures towards the teachers. Indeed, coping with teacher's emotional distress in response to the attitude of the students is a major stressor for teachers that influence intellectual functioning, self-efficacy, and motivation (Huang et al. 2019). In short, high levels of emotional distress can lead to burnout.

- 2.3. Teachers navigate a complex web of factors that can contribute to emotional distress (Kaslow et al., 2020). The educational system itself presents challenges. Balancing adherence to its standards with the need for updates can be a constant source of pressure (Sanchez et al., 2019). Similarly, school activities, planned and executed by teachers, must adhere to tight schedules to accommodate a packed curriculum. This pressure to deliver quality education within a limited timeframe can be frustrating (Neppl et al., 2020).

According to Sanchez et al (2019) perhaps the most significant source of emotional distress comes from evaluations by superiors. These assessments determine a teacher's eligibility, competence, and overall performance. Unsatisfactory feedback from a school head can lead to disappointment and a decline in self-esteem (Kaslow et al., 2020).

As highlighted by Neppl et al. (2020), based on Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT), emotional distress often stems from how we evaluate ourselves and situations. These evaluations can be irrational, characterized by self-downing, dramatization, and a sense of imperativeness (Bora et al., 2018). Some teachers might believe they have complete control over the situation due to their expertise. Others might even tie their self-worth to their professional performance, viewing success at work as synonymous with life success (Bora et al., 2018). These types of irrational beliefs can exacerbate the emotional impact of negative evaluations.

- 2.4. Studies have shown that teachers who struggle to accept and manage emotional and physical stress, or who have a lower tolerance for intense emotions, are more likely to experience negative consequences (Pugach et al., 2020; Boelen 2021; Appe & Teclh 2020). These consequences can include:(a) Increased anxiety and

panic attacks: Teachers experiencing emotional distress may become more self-conscious and anxious, and even develop anxiety disorders (Pugach et al., 2020).(b) Fear of future distress: They may develop a fear of situations that previously caused them distress, leading them to become more cautious or avoidant in their behavior (Boelen, 2021).(c) Escape behaviors: Some teachers may resort to escape behaviors in response to physical symptoms of anxiety (Appe & Telch, 2020).

Furthermore, negative effects are evident in the school climate, it lowers teachers' empowerment, less chances of achieving learning goals, and increases the chances of teachers in deciding career change if they fail to overcome or regulate stress in short time (Pugach et al 2020). It is for the reason that teachers are no longer confident on what they can provide in the learning process and also because they are already worn out by the process.

2.5. The teaching profession faces a concerning trend of teacher attrition, with both new and experienced educators leaving the field (Karakose, Yirci,& Papadakis (2022). Many departing teachers cite emotional exhaustion or burnout as a significant factor. High workloads, low salaries, student discipline issues, and a lack of administrative support all contribute to this feeling of burnout (Al-Rabiaah et al.,2020).

According to Gustems-Carnicer,Calderón & Calderón-Garrido (2019) this emotional distress can be detrimental to a teacher's effectiveness. He suggests that it hinders teachers from reaching their full potential and delivering instruction effectively (Gustems Carnicer,Calderón & Calderón-Garrido (2019). Fortunately, there are approaches to managing emotional stress.

One promising strategy is mindfulness, which promotes emotional regulation skills from a "top-down" perspective (Al-Rabiaah et al.,2020). By developing these skills, teachers can lessen emotional distress and improve their ability to focus. This leads to a more productive and healthy lifestyle overall (Karakose, Yirci,& Papadakis (2022).

Furthermore, in essence, teachers who can effectively manage stress are better equipped to handle challenges and remain positive. They can then concentrate their energy on productive endeavors, which in turn can lessen the impact of emotional distress (Karakose, Yirci,& Papadakis (2022). This creates a positive cycle that benefits both teachers and students.

3. Regression analysis of Communication practices of Principals on Teachers Emotional distress

According to Collie (2021) investigates the impact of principals' emotional intelligence and instructional leadership on teachers' instructional strategies. Their findings, based on a sample of Chinese primary teachers, suggest that both a

principal's EI and their leadership behavior significantly influence the instructional strategies employed by teachers. This research is particularly noteworthy as it emphasizes the role of emotional intelligence in improving teaching practices and evaluating principal effectiveness.

Furthermore, an study by Chen and Guo (2020) stated that the the focus to teacher well-being and its connection to student outcomes shifts. They investigate the link between teacher emotion regulation skills, occupational health (burnout), and life satisfaction with student well-being. Drawing on data from elementary teachers and their students, the study reveals a significant association between teacher well-being and student outcomes. Specifically, teachers' use of cognitive reappraisal strategies related to lower student emotional distress, while expressive suppression was linked to students reporting a less positive outlook and peers observing fewer prosocial behaviors. Additionally, teacher life satisfaction was associated with higher levels of prosocial behavior in students.

4. Intervention Plan Based on the Findings of the Study

Rationale: The intervention plan for communication practices of principals and emotional distress of teachers aims to address a pressing issue that can have significant consequences for the overall well-being and productivity of educators. The rationale behind this plan is rooted in the recognition of the crucial role that effective communication plays in creating a positive and supportive work environment, as well as the detrimental impact that emotional distress can have on individual teachers and the overall functioning of the educational institution.

KRA	Strategies	Objective	Person/s Involved	Timeline	Sources	Success Indicators
Communication Practices	Seminar on Effective Communication Practices	To improve the communication skills of the principals as regards to their important roles to their teachers.	Principals	August 2023	Speakers, School Funds	100% attendance of principals
Emotional Distress	Seminar on Handling Emotional Distress	To provide teachers' emotional distress management with the experts	Teachers	August 2023	Speakers, School Funds	100% attendance of teachers

Conclusions

Considering the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Communication practices were evident among the principals. They had positive views about their overall communication practices, indicating that they believe they could communicate well with their teachers especially on the area of open communication.

2. Teachers have a slight distress which showed that teachers had a hard time with their lives as teachers which normally brought by the demands in their career and heavy workloads.
3. Principals' communication practices do not have significant impact on teachers' emotional distress. The null hypothesis was accepted.
4. An interventional was proposed based on the findings of the study focusing lowest scores on the communication practices of principals and emotional distress of the teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were hereby submitted:

1. To foster a positive school environment and safeguard teacher well-being, school leaders should prioritize respectful and constructive communication practices. This might involve implementing training programs focused on effective communication strategies for principals.
2. The researcher recommends incorporating self-reported measures of teacher well-being alongside behavioral observations and providing resources on managing emotional distress to gain a comprehensive picture.
3. The study found no significant impact of communication styles on teacher emotional distress, suggesting further research, and promoting open communication and collaboration between principals and teachers for a supportive school environment.
4. An intervention plan is a helpful basis for school management system as it offers a research-based foundation in formulating relevant programs and projects in obtaining better performance as whole.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured the ethical conduct of the study by following established research protocols. This included obtaining informed consent from all participants after they were provided with a detailed participant information sheet explaining the study's goals, methods, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time.

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